

PROOF:- how a convex mirror forms two images of an object by Anayat Manzoor (ayntheanu)

About the Experimenter – Anayat Manzoor (Ayn)

I am Anayat Manzoor, known as Ayn, a science student at Imperial Institute, Kulgam. With a deep interest in optics and experimental physics, I have conducted a unique experiment that proves a convex mirror can form two images of a single object, challenging the traditional understanding of image formation.

Apart from science, I am also an author of several books, including:

First Love, First Heartbreak

The Mirror Effect

Sunset in a Broken Mirror

The Sky Within Me

Again in Dark Era

The 1% Rule

Why or Why Not Education (Upcoming)

This experiment reflects my curiosity to go beyond textbooks and explore the hidden possibilities in science.

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A single convex mirror can form two images of a single object at same time. It is due to presence of some minutes dust particles and some gases CFC'S,CO₂,O₂,N₂(in high concentration). This medium is called ayononium medium

REASON FOR FORMATION OF 2ND IMAGE:

Gases like co₂,o₂,cfc are transparent but some of the light gets reflected by large angles and if the same lights reaches the mirror the second image is formed on the same mirror

The formula for calculating image distance, object distance and the focal length will be same

$$1/f=1/v\pm 1/u$$